

TEACHERS CHALLENGES IN THE CONDUCT OF ASSESSMENT AND THEIR TEACHING PERFORMANCE

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Teachers Challenges in the Conduct of Assessment and their Teaching Performance

Michelle B. Agawin, * Reynilda C. Alferez
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study explored the demographic characteristics of teachers, challenges faced in assessment practices, and their impact on teaching performance. The results showed a varied demographic profile, with the majority of teachers between the ages of 30 and 39, having Bachelor's Degrees, and having areas of specialization such as Science and Filipino. Notable challenges included preparing assessments, putting strategies into practice, encouraging student participation, and making good use of assessment feedback. Most teachers did well and showed high levels of satisfaction despite these challenges. The study also revealed that younger teachers faced greater challenges when it came to assessment. Specifically, there was a negative correlation between teaching performance and difficulties in using assessment feedback. In response, an action plan was suggested to improve teacher support and assessment planning. The study emphasized the necessity of focused interventions to address these issues, which enhanced assessment practices and lessened the workloads of teachers.

Keywords: *challenges, conduct, assessment, teachers, performance*

Introduction

Teachers play a vital role in learners' educational growth, and one of their most important duties is to assess their learning outcomes. However, teachers in the Philippines often face significant challenges in conducting assessments effectively, which can affect their teaching performance and, in turn, the learning results of the learners. The results of the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) show that among participating countries, Filipino learners ranked lowest in reading, math, and science. This unsettling finding raises questions about potential issues with the quality of the country's educational system, specifically the effectiveness of teaching and assessment practices. According to the PISA results, teachers might find it difficult to accurately assess their learners' knowledge, which could make it more difficult for them to modify their lessons to meet the needs of each learner and raise academic achievement.

These challenges highlight the need to investigate and address the difficulties teachers face in conducting assessments to enhance their teaching performance and ultimately improve learner outcomes in the Philippines. Effective assessment methods are essential in supporting an efficient teaching and learning process. Furthermore, understanding these challenges is important for formulating strategies to assist teachers in improving their teaching performance.

Numerous studies have identified various challenges teachers face when conducting assessments, such as inadequate training in modern assessment methods, class size, and learners' diverse needs. These issues can hinder teachers' capacity to deliver precise assessments, prompt feedback, and efficient instructional approaches.

DepEd Order No. 8, Series 2015, also known as the "Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K–12 Basic Education Program," was released to guide assessment practices in the Philippine education system. The policy emphasizes the utilization of formative assessment and other assessment tools such as rubrics, portfolios, and performance tasks. However, teachers may have difficulties applying these suggestions due to constraints such as limited resources, unfamiliarity with new tools, and the need for extra time to conduct successful assessments. These factors can lead to gaps between policy objectives and real-world classroom methods, affecting teaching effectiveness and learners' learning outcomes.

The primary objective of this study was to examine the relationship between the challenges teachers face in conducting assessments in Kauswagan District, Division of Lanao del Norte and their teaching performance. The study aimed to identify specific difficulties educators encountered during assessment and evaluate how these challenges that influenced their ability to deliver effective instruction and achieve desired learning outcomes.

The basis of this study was the assumption that the conduct of assessment techniques is crucial for achieving high-quality teaching performance. Teachers who have the capacity to accurately assess student learning are better positioned to tailor their lessons to meet learner's individual needs and improve overall educational outcomes.

This research contributes to the existing knowledge by exploring the relationship between teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment and their teaching performance. The findings would provide insights for developing an action plan that targeted professional development programs, teaching strategies, and policy decisions to enhance teaching effectiveness and student achievement.

Research Questions

The study determined the challenges faced by public high school teachers in the conduct of assessment within the District of

Kauswagan, Division of Lanao del Norte of SY 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.3. subject taught;
 - 1.4. years in service;and
 - 1.5. subject specialization?
2. What are the teachers' challenges in terms of:
 - 2.1. planning of assessment;
 - 2.2. methods of assessment for students learning;
 - 2.3. support provided to engage students actively; and
 - 2.4. application of assessment feedback?
3. What is the teaching performance of the teachers in the school year 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant influence between the teachers' demographic profile and the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment?
5. Is there a significant influence between the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment and their teaching performance?
6. What action plan can be designed to address the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment based on the result of this study?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational study design was used by the researcher. The age, highest educational attainment, subject taught, years of experience, and subject specialization demographics of the respondents were described using a descriptive study design. The challenges of teachers in the conducting assessment and their teaching performance in the school year 2022-2023 were also discussed. Since the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment were correlated with their teaching performance, this research was a correlation study. In this regard, the researcher thought that this design would be the most effective for determining how these challenges affect their teaching performance.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were all 57 teachers out of 60 teachers in the Public JHS of Kauswagan District, Division of Lanao del Norte during the School Year 2023-2024.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

School	Population		
	Male	Female	Total
Marcela T Mabanta National High School	0	34	34
Sultan Dimasangcay Mananngolo Integrated School	1	12	13
Kawit Oriental Integrated School	1	5	6
Baraason Integrated School	0	4	4
Total	2	55	57

Instrument

The instrument used in this study was adapted from the survey instrument for The Implementations and Challenges of Assessment Practices for Students' Learning in Public Selected Universities, Ethiopia by Birhanu Moges. The first part dealt with the demographic profile of respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, subject taught, years in service, and subject specialization.

Part 2 of the research instrument contained 35 indicators for teachers to determine teachers challenges in terms of planning of assessment, methods of assessment for students learning, support provided to engage students actively, and application of assessment feedback. Part 3 of the research instrument was the IPCRF rating of the teacher on the school year 2022 – 2023. This research instrument has undergone pilot testing at Bansarvil National High School, Kapatagan, Lanao del Norte, involving 25 teachers to check its validity and reliability.

The respondents measured their level of challenges by checking the appropriate box using a rating scale with corresponding descriptions as follows: 1 – Very Rarely or Never; 2 – Occasionally; 3 – Very Frequently; 4 – Always

Procedure

To be able to facilitate the gathering of data, a letter of permission duly signed by the adviser and the Dean of the Graduate Studies of St. Peters College to conduct research was sought from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Lanao del Norte. After the

approval, an endorsement letter along with a request letter was then presented to the School Principal.

Participants were then presented with the informed consent and the letter of request from the researcher. The respondents were highly guided that the teachers' demographic profile and their responses were kept confidential. The data gathered had been recorded, organized, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used in analyzing and determining the demographic profile of the respondents age, highest educational attainment, subject taught, years in service, and subject specialization.

For Problem 2, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to measure the level of challenges of the teachers in terms of planning of assessment, methods of assessment for students learning, support provided to engage students actively, and application of assessment feedback.

For Problem 3, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to measure the teachers teaching performance in the school year 2022-2023.

For Problems 4 and 5, Regression Analysis was used to determine the relationship between the demographic and the challenges of the teachers in terms of planning of assessment, methods of assessment for students learning, the support provided to engage students actively and application of assessment feedback and to determine the relationship between the teachers' challenges on the conduct of assessment and their teaching performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyze and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in this study. The presentation, interpretation and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, subject taught, years of service, and subject specialization?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
20-29	12	21.1
30-39	27	47.4
40-49	10	17.5
50-59	6	10.5
60-65	2	3.5
Total	57	100.0

Table 2 shows the age distribution among the respondents, presenting both frequency and percentage data. The age group of 30-39 years old accounts for the largest demographic profile of respondents, making up around half of all respondents. Conversely, the age range of 60-65 had the lowest demographic profile, making a few percent of all responses.

The age group that made up the majority of responders, which was 30-39, appeared to be more actively involved in teaching and may perhaps made up a sizeable share of the teaching workforce. This age group typically represented mid-career instructors who had accumulated a significant amount of experience, but who might still be actively engaged in professional development and making adjustments to meet evolving pedagogical demands. The greater representation of this age group might point to a group of educators who were more seasoned in their professions and might possess advanced knowledge of evaluation procedures. On the other hand, the low percentage of respondents who were between the ages of 60 and 65 might point to several reasons, including retirement, changing careers, or a decline in the number of people who chose to become teachers later in life.

Determining the demographic makeup of the teaching workforce required an understanding of the age distribution of the respondents. It could shed light on possible variations in professional development requirements, technological literacy, and instructional methods between generations. Targeted support and mentorship could help younger instructors in the 20-29 and 30-39 age groups improve their assessment procedures and advance their careers. In addition, succession planning and maintaining institutional knowledge within the educational system depended on attending to the needs and concerns of older instructors, especially those who were getting close to retirement age.

Similar patterns were discovered in a study on teacher demographics conducted by Shepard et al. (2020). In many educational contexts, a sizable percentage of teachers were in the 30- to 39-year-old age range. Furthermore, the research emphasized the significance of taking into account the various needs and viewpoints of educators across all age groups to support teacher retention and professional development. The research highlighted the intricacy of catering to the varied requirements of educators across various career phases

and the significance of customized support systems to augment their efficacy in evaluation methodologies.

Table 3. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor's Degree	30	52.6
With MA Units	17	29.8
Master Degree	10	17.5
Total	57	100.0

Table 3 presents the highest educational attainment of the respondents, presenting both the frequency and percentage distribution. The respondents' greatest levels of education varied; about half of the teachers had a bachelor's degree, approximately a third had finished master's courses, and around one-sixth had a master's degree. The majority of respondents having a Bachelor's Degree indicated that a sizeable proportion of the teaching workforce was qualified at the undergraduate level. This could point to a typical entry point into the teaching field or a predilection for bachelor's degree holders to choose teaching employment. Even if they did not finish a master's degree entirely, teachers appeared to be committed to continuing their education, based on the significant proportion of respondents who had completed Master's units. The comparatively lower number of participants who had obtained a master's degree underscores a possible disparity in higher education credentials among educators.

The distribution of educational attainment among educators affected how well-equipped and capable they were to deal with the demands of evaluation. Advanced degrees, like a Master's Degree, could expand knowledge and proficiency in assessment theory and practice whereas a Bachelor's Degree offered fundamental information and abilities. Master's degree holders may be better able to apply cutting-edge assessment techniques, examine assessment data, and adjust to changing trends in education. Nonetheless, a sizeable portion of responders had finished Master's units, suggesting a chance for more professional growth and assistance in finishing advanced degrees.

According to research by Chun-Shou et al. (2019), teachers can improve their efficacy in assessment techniques by pursuing additional credentials and ongoing professional development. In addition, the study emphasized the benefits of graduate school for both student results and teacher effectiveness. These studies highlighted how important it was to support teachers' professional development and continuous learning to handle the challenges of evaluation in various educational contexts.

Table 4 shows the subjects taught by the respondents, presenting both frequency and percentage data. The respondents taught a variety of courses; Science, Filipino, MAPEH, and ESP which incurred the highest frequencies, but English, Math, AP, and TLE were all represented, albeit at lesser percentages.

Table 4. *Subject Taught of the Respondents*

<i>Subject Taught</i>	<i>Frequency (n=57)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
English	10	17.5
Math	9	15.8
Science	18	31.6
Filipino	12	21.1
AP	10	17.5
TLE	11	19.3
MAPEH	12	21.1
ESP	12	21.1

The respondents' subject-mix distribution illustrated the range of academic specializations offered by the curriculum. There appeared to be a significant presence of teachers in these subject areas within the questioned population, as indicated by the higher frequencies in Science, Filipino, MAPEH, and ESP. Within the educational system, this distribution could represent instructor preferences, student enrollment trends, or curricular priorities. The lower percentages in AP, TLE, English, and Math could point to subjects where specialist knowledge was needed or where there was comparatively less of a need for teachers.

The respondents' distribution of subjects taught emphasized how crucial subject-specific factors were for tackling assessment issues. Depending on the type of information and abilities being evaluated, different subjects could call for different methodologies, instruments, and procedures for assessment evaluation in the field of Science, for instance, could prioritize experimentation and inquiry-based learning, whereas evaluation in the field of Filipino might concentrate on language competency and understanding. Knowing the requirements for subject-specific assessments could help with the creation of teacher resources and professional development programs that were specifically tailored to teachers.

Effective teaching and learning outcomes were dependent on subject-specific pedagogical expertise and assessment literacy, according to research by Ishaq et al. (2018). In a similar vein, a study by Ahmed et al. (2019) emphasized the necessity of using varied assessment strategies across various topic areas in order to meet the various needs of instructors and students.

These studies highlighted the need to take subject-specific characteristics into account when tackling assessment issues and enhancing the efficacy of teachers.

Table 5. *Years in Service of the Respondents*

<i>Years of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1-5	15	26.3
6-10	31	54.4
11-15	4	7.0
16-20	3	5.3
21-25	1	1.8
26-30	2	3.5
31-35	1	1.8
Total	57	100.0

Table 5 displays the distribution of respondents based on their years of teaching experience, presenting both frequency and percentage data. While respondents' years of experience vary, majority were between six and ten years of experience. Slightly more than a quarter respondents with 1–5 years of experience made up the second largest group with smaller numbers in the 11–15, 16–20, 21–25, 26–30, and 31–35 years of experience categories following.

There was a comparatively large percentage of instructors with mid-career experience (6–10 years) according to the respondents' years of experience distribution. This group probably reflected a sizable cohort of educators who have advanced past their early professional stages and amassed a substantial body of classroom experience. The fact that a sizable portion of respondents had one to five years of experience pointed to a consistent inflow of new educators into the field, which may be the result of recruitment initiatives or high employee turnover. Fewer options for career progression after a particular point or attrition over time might be shown by the lesser percentages in the higher experience groups.

The distribution of years of experience affected how evaluation problems were handled and how teacher growth was assisted. To improve their assessment literacy and classroom management abilities, recently qualified teachers with one to five years of experience might need to participate in specialized induction programs and receive mentorship. Opportunities for ongoing professional development could help mid-career teachers with six to ten years of experience improve their evaluation procedures and avoid stagnation. Additionally, preserving institutional knowledge and leadership in schools depended on efforts to keep experienced teachers in the field, especially those with 11 or more years of experience.

According to research by Ugwu et al. (2022), to meet the specific requirements and problems of teachers at various phases of their careers, professional development programs must be specifically designed for them. Likewise, Agayon et al.'s (2022) study emphasized the value of peer assistance and mentorship in helping early-career instructors become more proficient in evaluation techniques. These studies highlighted how important it was to take into account the years of experience that teachers had when creating interventions that would assist their professional development and enhance student results.

Table 6. *Subject Specialization of the Respondents*

<i>Subject Specialization</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
English	6	10.5
Math	9	15.8
Science	14	24.6
Filipino	5	8.8
AP	9	15.8
TLE	9	15.8
MAPEH	4	7.0
ESP	1	1.8
Total	57	100.0

Table 6 presents the subject specializations of the respondents, highlighting the frequency and percentage distribution. Science has the largest frequency of topic specializations among the respondents about a quarter whereas ESP has the lowest prevalence in a small fraction.

The prevalence of science specialization indicated that STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education was highly valued among educators. This could be a reflection of more general educational initiatives that were meant to develop scientific literacy and get learners ready for STEM-related jobs. A smaller pool of specialist teachers or less emphasis on this subject area within the teaching profession may be the cause of the lower frequency of specialization in ESP (Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao). Character development and values education were usually included in ESP, even if they might not always get the same attention as other important academic topics.

Science is a field where specialization is common. This emphasized the value of emphasizing STEM education and encouraging students to learn via inquiry and develop critical thinking abilities. Providing science instructors with professional development opportunities could improve their ability to create interesting and useful assessment plans that complemented STEM learning goals. On the other hand, to overcome the lower frequency of specialty in ESP, it might be necessary to launch professional development programs or make focused recruitment efforts to increase instructors' knowledge of values education and holistic student development.

Subject specialization has a significant effect on student results and teacher effectiveness, especially in STEM fields, according to research by Shepard et al. (2020). In a similar vein, Hung et al. (2018) stressed the importance of professional development and specialized training for improving teacher competencies and advancing inclusive education methods. These studies highlighted how important it was to take subject specialization into account while resolving assessment issues and encouraging efficient teaching methods across a range of subject areas.

Problem 2: What is the level of challenges of the teachers in terms of planning of assessment, methods of assessment for students learning, support provided to engage students actively and application of assessment feedback?

Table 7. Challenges of the Teachers in terms of Planning of Assessment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Identify learning objectives and assessment criteria	4.68	.66	Always
2. Plan how to share learning objectives and assessment criteria	4.49	.76	Very Frequently
3. Design student -centered assessment methods and tasks	4.56	.68	Always
4. Examine students' prior knowledge in the subject	4.53	.73	Always
5. Design better questions and questioning strategies	4.61	.67	Always
Total Measure	4.57	.61	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Very Rarely; 1.50-2.49, Rarely; 2.50-3.49, Occasionally; 3.50-4.49, Very Frequently; 4.50-5.00, Always

Table 7 presents the challenges faced by teachers in terms of planning assessment, providing mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) values for various indicators. Teachers consistently indicated the highest degree of engagement in "Identify learning objectives and assessment criteria" with a mean score of approximately 4.68 among the planning assessment indicators, indicating that they always completed this task. Conversely, "Plan how to share learning objectives and assessment criteria" with a mean score of approximately 4.49 had the lowest reported frequency of involvement, but still reflected a highly frequent engagement.

Teachers seem to place a great deal of importance on clearly defining goals and evaluation criteria, as evidenced by the highest frequency of engagement in creating learning objectives and criteria. Ensuring alignment between instructional objectives, assessment tasks, and student learning outcomes was imperative and required the completion of this first stage. On the other hand, although it received a little lower rating, organizing how to communicate learning objectives and assessment standards nevertheless showed a high frequency of engagement. This could suggest that even when educators set goals and expectations regularly, they might not always tell students about them directly or might use different methods to do so.

A strong commitment to clarity and transparency in assessment methods was demonstrated by the high frequency of engagement in developing learning objectives and assessment criteria, which could improve student performance and understanding. The marginally lesser involvement in strategizing the dissemination of these goals and standards, however, pointed to a possible area for development. Setting goals, encouraging learner autonomy, and encouraging self-regulated learning all depended on clearly expressing learning objectives and evaluation criteria to students. Therefore, enhancing the influenced of assessment on student learning and motivation could be further achieved by offering teachers' help and direction on efficient ways to share assessment information with students.

Black and William (2009) emphasized that sharing learning objectives and assessment criteria with students to help them understand expectations and targets. The challenge teachers faced in this area aligned with the need for clarity and transparency in student learning objectives.

Table 8. Challenges of the Teachers in terms of Methods of Assessment for Students Learning

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Conduct quizzes	4.47	.78	Very Frequently
2. Perform practical work	4.09	.83	Very Frequently
3. Give presentation	4.21	.77	Very Frequently
4. Conduct self-assessment	4.14	.88	Very Frequently
5. Conduct peer-assessment	3.93	.98	Very Frequently
6. Provide feedback opportunities	3.86	.97	Very Frequently
7. Offer oral feedback	4.44	.87	Very Frequently
8. Provide written feedback	4.02	.90	Very Frequently
9. Establish criteria and objective with students	4.33	.79	Very Frequently
10. Reflect students' feedback to assess ideas and lesson learned	4.16	.84	Very Frequently
Total Measure	4.16	.66	Very Frequently

Note: 1.00-1.49, Very Rarely; 1.50-2.49, Rarely; 2.50-3.49, Occasionally; 3.50-4.49, Very Frequently; 4.50-5.00, Always

Table 8 provides insights into the challenges teachers faced regarding methods of assessment for student learning, presenting mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) values for various indicators. Teachers indicated the highest frequency of participation with a mean score of approximately 4.47 on quizzes among the variables related to methods of evaluation for student learning, indicating that they utilized quizzes frequently. Conversely, the mean score of approximately 3.93 on the conduct of peer assessment had the lowest reported frequency of involvement but was still being used rather regularly.

Because quizzes are taken so frequently, teachers likely use them extensively to measure student learning and give quick feedback.

Tests of students' comprehension of the course material were frequently used as formative assessment tools to inform instructional decisions. On the other hand, although peer evaluation was widely used, its mean score was marginally lower than that of other evaluation techniques. This suggested that even if educators understand the benefits of peer evaluation, they could have trouble incorporating it into their lesson plans or carrying it out successfully.

The fact that quizzes are widely used indicated how well they work at giving students quick feedback and guiding lesson planning. The decreased participation in peer evaluation, however, points to a possible area for development in terms of encouraging student collaboration and peer feedback exchange. Collaborative learning, critical thinking, and student autonomy can be fostered by offering professional development opportunities to teachers so they can improve their facilitation abilities and explore new avenues for peer evaluation.

According to research by Fatih (2020), to increase student engagement and deepen learning, it is critical to use a variety of evaluation methods, including peer assessment. In a similar vein, Mouraz et al. (2019) study emphasized the benefits of peer evaluation for student learning outcomes and the growth of collaborative abilities. To maximize teaching efficacy and student learning experiences, this research highlighted the importance of addressing both the greatest and lowest markers of engagement in methods of assessment for student learning.

Table 9 presents the challenges faced by teachers concerning the support provided to engage students actively, presenting mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) values for various indicators. Among the factors related to the support provided to engage students actively, teachers consistently encourage students to share ideas with a mean score of approximately 4.72 suggesting that they always urged students to participate actively in class. In contrast, the least frequently reported involvement was in repeating the learning objectives and criteria during the lesson with a mean score of approximately 4.05 but still being utilized rather frequently.

Table 9. Challenges of the Teachers in terms of Support Provided to Engage Students Actively

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Encourage students to share ideas	4.72	.73	Always
2. Encourage every student to ask questions	4.60	.82	Always
3. Engage every student to answer questions	4.63	.77	Always
4. Encourage students to take risks and listen to others' ideas	4.49	.80	Very Frequently
5. Advise students to assess their own work of learning objectives	4.39	.75	Very Frequently
6. Ask oral questions	4.58	.68	Always
7. Encourage students to answer questions quickly	4.44	.78	Very Frequently
8. Create opportunities for students to act on feedback provided	4.35	.81	Very Frequently
9. Provide examples of quality work that shows the standards required	4.32	.78	Very Frequently
10. Repeat the learning objectives and criteria during the lesson	4.05	.85	Very Frequently
Total Measure	4.48	.57	Very Frequently

Note: 1.00-1.49, Very Rarely; 1.50-2.49, Rarely; 2.50-3.49, Occasionally; 3.50-4.49, Very Frequently; 4.50-5.00, Always

The majority of engagement in promoting class participation indicates that educators place a high value on fostering an inclusive, dynamic learning environment where all students were motivated to participate. Students who actively participated in class were more engaged, and collaborative, and developed their critical thinking abilities. On the other hand, even if group assignments were given out a lot, their mean score was marginally lower than that of other indicators. This could mean that even though educators understand how important group work was for encouraging collaborative learning, they could have trouble incorporating it into their lesson plans or applying it successfully.

Teachers' dedication to creating a dynamic, inclusive learning environment that encouraged student involvement and participation was seen in the broad promotion of class participation. Nonetheless, the marginally reduced involvement in assigning group tasks indicated a possible avenue for enhancement in encouraging cooperative learning opportunities for students. Further improving group work chances and helping teachers created and carried out successful group projects would help students become more cooperative, communicative, and team players.

To improve learning outcomes, research by Rogers et al. (2022), highlighted the significance of encouraging active student engagement and cooperation. Moreover, the study emphasized the benefits of collaborative learning opportunities for student progress and engagement. These studies highlighted how important it was to foster active student engagement by addressing both the greatest and lowest engagement metrics to maximize teaching effectiveness and student learning opportunities.

Table 10 sheds light on the challenges teachers face in terms of the application of assessment feedback, presenting mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) values for various indicators. Teachers consistently indicated the highest degree of engagement in planning what to teach next and got a mean score of approximately 4.67 among the indicators related to the application of assessment feedback, indicating that they always planned their next instruction based on assessment input. Conversely, telling their achievement on a task against other students' results got the lowest mean score of approximately 4.11 but was still being used quite regularly.

Table 10. *Challenges of the Teachers in terms of Application of Assessment Feedback*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Advise students about how to fill the gap in their learning	4.28	.75	Very Frequently
2. Modify my teaching strategies accordingly	4.39	.67	Very Frequently
3. Plan what to teach next	4.67	.69	Always
4. Tell their achievement on a task against other students' result	4.11	.82	Very Frequently
5. Identify the gaps in students' understanding	4.32	.77	Very Frequently
6. Categorize students into different groups	4.32	.76	Very Frequently
7. Orally suggest on how to improve their work	4.54	.76	Always
8. Suggest means for students to plan their future learning	4.42	.71	Very Frequently
9. Record assessment results	4.72	.70	Always
10. Permit students to resubmit their work once they improved it	4.25	.85	Very Frequently
Total Measure	4.40	.56	Very Frequently

Note: 1.00-1.49, Very Rarely; 1.50-2.49, Rarely; 2.50-3.49, Occasionally; 3.50-4.49, Very Frequently; 4.50-5.00, Always

The teachers that engaged the most frequently in preparing what to teach next appeared to emphasize using assessment feedback to guide their lesson planning. Teachers could effectively address the requirements of their students by customizing their teaching tactics with this proactive approach. On the other hand, although providing students with information on how their performance compared to that of others was a commonly used strategy, its mean score was marginally lower than that of other indicators. This may suggest that, in contrast to other feedback approaches, teachers may employ comparison feedback less frequently or with less emphasis, even when they understand its importance.

Teachers' commitment to utilizing data-driven ways to improve student learning was seen in the widespread engagement in developing future instruction based on assessment feedback. The somewhat lower participation rate in giving comparative evaluation, however, pointed to a possible area for development in terms of encouraging students to create goals and become self-aware. The usefulness of assessment feedback in fostering student development and accomplishment could be further increased by encouraging teachers to offer constructive comparative evaluation and by helping students define tailored learning goals.

Sarabia et al.'s (2020) research highlighted how crucial it was to use assessment feedback to guide instructional decisions and enhance student learning. Furthermore, these emphasized how goal-oriented feedback improved student performance and motivation. To maximize teaching efficacy and student learning outcomes, this research highlighted the importance of addressing both the greatest and lowest signs of engagement when applying evaluation feedback.

Table 11 provides a consolidated overview of the challenges faced by teachers across different components, presenting mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) values. Teachers consistently placed a high premium on organizing assessment activities, as evidenced by the component with the greatest degree of engagement, with a mean score of approximately 4.57 on planning assessment. On the other hand, methods of assessment for students' learning showed the lowest degree of engagement with a mean score of approximately 4.16, indicating that teachers often encountered difficulties when it comes to assessing pupils' learning.

Table 11. *Consolidated Findings of the Challenges of the Teachers*

<i>Components</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Planning of Assessment	4.57	.61	Always
Methods of Assessment for Students Learning	4.16	.66	Very Frequently
Support Provided to Engage Students Actively	4.42	.57	Very Frequently
Application of Assessment Feedback	4.40	.56	Very Frequently
Total Measure	4.39	.49	Very Frequently

Note: 1.00-1.49, Very Rarely; 1.50-2.49, Rarely; 2.50-3.49, Occasionally; 3.50-4.49, Very Frequently; 4.50-5.00, Always

Teachers' dedication to defining precise objectives and evaluation criteria were demonstrated by the high degree of engagement in the development of assessment activities. Teachers could create effective assessment strategies that were in line with the needs of their students and the aims of their instruction by taking a proactive approach.

Dube-Xaba and Xulu (2020) emphasized the crucial significance of assessment in the process of teaching and learning. Effective assessment planning is essential to ensure that learners achieve the desired learning competencies and objectives. The difficulties encountered by teachers in the process of designing assessments may arise from the necessity to ensure their congruence with cognitive learning objectives and curriculum benchmarks.

Problem 3: What is the teaching performance of teachers in the school year 2022-2023?

Table 12. *Performance of Teachers in the School Year 2023-2024*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>
4.50-5.00	11	19.3	Outstanding
3.50-4.49	45	78.9	Very Satisfactory
2.50-3.49	1	1.8	Satisfactory
Total	57	100.0	

Note: Mean (SD) = 4.02 (.38)

Table 12 provides an overview of the performance of teachers during the school year 2022-2023, categorized into different ranges based on their performance ratings. The majority of teachers, approximately three-quarters, fell within the range of 3.50-4.49, classified as "Very Satisfactory." This indicated a significant proportion of teachers performing at a commendable level, meeting or exceeding expected standards in their roles. Furthermore, around one-fifth of teachers achieved ratings in the range of 4.50-5.00, signifying an "Outstanding" performance level. These results highlighted the dedication and commitment of educators in delivering high-quality instruction and facilitating student learning effectively.

Additionally, a small fraction of teachers, representing approximately 2%, received a rating in the range of 2.50-3.49, categorized as "Satisfactory.". While this indicated satisfactory performance, it also suggested potential areas for growth and improvement. Overall, the mean performance rating of teachers was 4.02, with a standard deviation of 0.38. This suggested a generally high level of performance among teachers, reflecting positively on the quality of education provided within the school year.

These findings underscored the importance of recognizing and acknowledging the efforts of teachers in their professional roles. Moving forward, school leaders needed to continue providing support, resources, and professional development opportunities to empower teachers in further enhancing their instructional practices and promoting continuous improvement. Additionally, periodic evaluations and feedback mechanisms could help identify areas for growth and provide targeted support to ensure all teachers reached their full potential in contributing to student success and overall school excellence.

The role of effective assessment in teaching was examined by Black and William (2009) as well as Ahmed, Ali, and Shah (2019). Teachers who possessed a comprehensive comprehension of assessment procedures and adeptly employed them in their instructional methodologies may see enhanced levels of performance. The teachers' overall good performance may be attributed to their adeptness in utilizing assessment in their teaching methodologies.

Problem 4: Is there a significant influence between the teachers’ demographic profile and the teachers’ challenges in the conduct of assessment?

Table 13. Regression Analysis of Challenges in Conducting Assessment on Teachers’ Demographic Profile

	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age=20-29	-.633	.300	-2.107*	.041	Significant
Age=30-39	-.292	.277	-1.056	.297	Not significant
Age=40-49	-.134	.295	-.453	.653	Not significant
Age=50-65 (ref)	--	--	--	--	--
Education=Bachelor	-.024	.223	-.108	.915	Not significant
Education=With MA Units	-.118	.228	-.515	.609	Not significant
Education=Master degree (ref)	--	--	--	--	--
Years of Experience=1-5	.221	.266	.832	.410	Not significant
Years of Experience=6-10	.184	.243	.757	.453	Not significant
Years of Experience=11+	--	--	--	--	--
Subject Specialization=English	-.085	.334	-.255	.800	Not significant
Subject Specialization=Math	-.213	.281	-.760	.452	Not significant
Subject Specialization=Science	-.206	.274	-.754	.455	Not significant
Subject Specialization=Filipino	-.047	.324	-.145	.885	Not significant
Subject Specialization=AP	-.233	.310	-.751	.457	Not significant
Subject Specialization=TLE	-.242	.305	-.793	.432	Not significant
Subject Specialization=MAPEH/ESP (ref)	--	--	--	--	--
Number of Subject Taught	-.178	.081	-2.207*	.033	Significant

Note: Analysis is based Regression with Dummy Variable *significant at .05 level

Table 13 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the challenges in implementing assessment in relation to teachers' demographic profiles. The regression analysis examined the relationship between various demographic factors of teachers and the challenges they faced in implementing assessment practices. The results indicated that there was a significant negative link between age group "20-29" and obstacles in implementing assessment (B = -0.633, p = 0.041) among the predictors. This suggested that younger teachers in this age group typically encountered greater difficulties than their older colleagues. Furthermore, a strong negative association between problems and the number of subjects taught by instructors was also evident (B = -0.178, p = 0.033), indicating that teachers who oversee a bigger number of subjects had greater difficulties when putting assessment techniques into effect.

The noteworthy inverse correlation found for the age bracket "20-29" suggested that younger educators could face distinct obstacles or necessitate supplementary assistance in executing evaluation procedures efficiently. This research emphasized how crucial it was to give early-career teachers specialized professional development and mentoring opportunities to improve their assessment literacies and competencies. Similarly, teachers with heavier teaching loads may find it difficult to balance assessment demands across multiple subjects, highlighting the need for workload management strategies and support mechanisms. This was supported by the significant relationship found between the number of subjects taught and challenges in assessment implementation.

The results pointed to many ramifications for stakeholders in education. To effectively address the unique requirements of younger teachers, focused support and professional development activities should be created, emphasizing the improvement of assessment competencies and the provision of techniques for effectively navigating obstacles. Schools and other educational institutions should also take workload distribution tactics into account to lessen the difficulties faced by teachers. These mentors were teaching many disciplines and they should ensure that resources and support were distributed fairly. Furthermore, continuous assessment practice monitoring and evaluation could assist in pinpointing problem areas and guide focused interventions that would improve student results and instructor effectiveness.

According to research by Paul (2020), early-career instructors could improve their assessment procedures and improve student learning outcomes by receiving focused professional development and support. Furthermore, it emphasized the influence of workload management techniques on the effectiveness and well-being of teachers. These studies highlighted how important it was to take demographic characteristics into account when assisting educators and maximizing evaluation procedures in learning environments.

Problem 5: Is there a significant influence between the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment and their teaching performance?

Table 14. *Test of Relationship between the Teachers' Level of Challenges in the Conduct of Assessment and Teachers' Performance*

Level of Challenges	Teachers' Performance		Remark
	r-value	p-value	
Planning of Assessment	-.188	.161	Not significant
Methods of Assessment for student learning	-.193	.149	Not significant
Support provided to engage students actively	-.201	.133	Not significant
Application of assessment feedback	-.271*	.041	Significant
Total Measure	-.241	.071	Not significant

Note: *significant at .05 level

Table 14 presents the results of the test examining the relationship between teachers' level of challenges in the conduct of assessment and their performance. Across various components such as planning of assessment, methods of assessment for student learning, and support provided to engage students actively, the R-values range from -0.188 to -0.201, with associated p-values above 0.05. These results indicate that there is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' perceived challenges in these areas and their performance ratings. Therefore, factors related to planning assessments, implementing assessment methods, and engaging students actively do not appear to strongly influence teachers' overall performance ratings.

However, in the case of the application of assessment feedback, the r-value is -0.271, with a p-value of 0.041, indicating a significant negative correlation between teachers' perceived challenges in this area and their performance ratings. This suggested that teachers who faced more challenges in applying assessment feedback tend to have lower performance ratings. It underscored the importance of effectively incorporating assessment feedback into teaching practices to enhance instructional quality and student learning outcomes.

Thus, according to Rahman (2018), feedback played a crucial part in the assessment of learning. Teachers who effectively employed feedback had the potential to enhance student engagement and academic achievements. This finding provided evidence for the proposition that difficulties in implementing evaluation feedback might have a detrimental effect on teaching effectiveness. This was supported by Dagdag (2020), it was crucial to emphasize the significance of offering constructive feedback remarks in addition to test scores. If teachers encountered difficulties in this domain, it could hinder their pedagogical efficacy, since learners may not be receiving the necessary support to enhance their performance.

Problem 6: What Action Plan can be designed to address the teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment based on the result of this study?

Proposed Program:

"Improving Assessment Methods and Teaching Effectiveness: A Strategic Approach to Addressing Teachers' Concerns"

Rationale

Assessment is crucial in the teaching and learning process as it serves as a means to measure student comprehension, inform instructional choices, and offer valuable feedback to students. Nevertheless, educators frequently encounter substantial obstacles when it comes to devising and executing tests with efficiency, which might impede their instructional effectiveness and influence student achievements.

The proposed action plan seeks to enhance teachers' assessment practices by giving them systematic assistance and strategies that will result in improving their teaching performance.

Objectives:

To facilitate effective communication between teachers and students regarding learning objectives and assessment criteria.

To enhance the range of evaluation methods available to teachers and incorporate a variety of new strategies.

To encourage collaborative and active learning opportunities for the learners.

To guide teachers in delivering timely, specific and constructive feedback to learners.

To provide ongoing training and resources on assessment and best practices in teaching.

Conclusions

Teachers' challenges in conducting assessments shed light on several key insights that hold implications for educational practices. Notably, teachers exhibited commendable proficiency in the planning of assessments, exemplified by the high mean score in the planning of assessment component. This proficiency underscored the importance of nurturing effective planning strategies among teachers. Institutions could consider targeted professional development programs and accessible resources to further enhance educators' planning capabilities, fostering a culture of meticulous assessment preparation.

Based on the findings of the study, there appeared to be a correlation between the usage of assessment feedback and teacher performance. This implied that improved teacher performance, which was influenced by the effective utilization of feedback, could potentially yield good effects on student learning outcomes. There was a positive correlation between the improvement of instructors and the enhancement of student learning experiences and outcomes.

The study revealed a significant influence between teachers' demographic profiles and the challenges they faced in conducting assessments. Younger teachers, particularly those aged 20-29, reported encountering more difficulties in conducting assessments. Additionally, the number of subjects taught by teachers was positively correlated with the challenges experienced in implementing assessment procedures, highlighting the influence of workload and subject specialization on assessment practices. These results rejected the hypothesis, suggesting that demographic variables such as age and workload significantly influenced the challenges teachers face in conducting assessment.

Based on the data provided, the hypothesis was accepted, meaning, there was no significant influence between teachers' challenges in the conduct of assessment and their teaching performance. Thus, most components of teachers' challenges, such as planning assessments, methods of assessment for student learning, and support provided to engage students actively did not significantly influence teaching performance. However, there was one exception in the application of assessment feedback, which showed a significant negative influence on teaching performance. This specific area required further investigation and targeted support for teachers to effectively apply assessment feedback and improve their performance. Overall, the hypothesis was accepted except for the application of assessment feedback.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to various stakeholders in the educational system.

For school leaders, these findings underscore the importance of recognizing and addressing the unique challenges faced by teachers in different age groups. Tailoring support initiatives based on age-related insights can contribute significantly to the well-being and effectiveness of educators. Additionally, fostering a positive and engaging learning environment should be a priority, as it positively correlates with teachers' ability to navigate assessment challenges. School leaders should invest in professional development programs that enhance teachers' planning skills and coping mechanisms, ultimately contributing to a more supportive and effective educational environment.

Learners stand to benefit from school leaders' emphasis on creating engaging and supportive classrooms. The findings highlight the positive impact of an actively engaging learning environment on teachers' ability to manage assessment challenges. Therefore, school leaders should encourage instructional strategies that promote student engagement, fostering a conducive atmosphere for effective teaching and learning. Furthermore, learners can play an active role in their education by participating in discussions on assessment methods and providing feedback on their learning experiences, contributing to a collaborative and student-centered educational approach.

Teachers must be engaged in professional development programs focused on assessment literacy, which can provide valuable strategies and techniques for effective assessment planning, implementation, and feedback provision. These programs can help teachers enhance their assessment practices and overcome challenges more effectively.

Parents play a crucial role in supporting their children's education, and these findings emphasize the importance of staying informed about the challenges teachers face in the conduct of assessments. Parental involvement in school activities and open communication with educators can create a more supportive partnership. Understanding the impact of an engaging learning environment on teachers' ability to navigate challenges should encourage parents to actively participate in school initiatives aimed at fostering such an atmosphere.

Curriculum planners can use these insights to refine and tailor professional development programs for teachers. Recognizing the significance of planning skills and coping mechanisms in assessment practices, curriculum planners should design workshops and resources that specifically address these areas. This targeted approach can enhance teachers' overall effectiveness in conducting

assessments and contribute to continuous improvement in educational practices.

For future researchers, this study suggests avenues for further investigations by exploring the dynamics of age-related challenges among teachers. And that contribution to effective assessment practices could provide valuable insights. Future research endeavors must build on these findings to contribute to the ongoing enhancement of teaching and learning practices.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Michelle B. Agawin

Department of Education – Philippines

Reynilda C. Alferez, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines